

EFFECTS OF POROSITY SHAPE ON THE ELECTROMECHANICAL RESPONSE OF 3-3 PIEZOELECTRIC FOAMS

B. Nguyen¹, K.S. Challagulla^{1*}

¹ Bharti School of Engineering, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Canada

* Corresponding author (kchallagulla@laurentian.ca)

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1 Introduction

Porous piezoelectric materials by virtue of their unique electromechanical coupling characteristics, signal-to-noise ratio, impedance matching, piezoelectric charge coefficients (d_h), and hydrostatic figures of merit (d_{hg}), play a prominent role in the modern electro-ceramic industry. Applications of porous piezoelectric materials include hydrophones, vibratory sensors, miniature accelerometers, and contact microphones [1]. Porous piezoelectric materials can be broadly classified as 3-0 type (where the porosity is enclosed in all three dimensions by a matrix phase), 3-1 type (where the porosity exhibits connectivity in the 1-direction and the matrix phase is connected in all three directions), and 3-3 type (where the porosity exists in an open interconnecting network where both the porosity and matrix phase exhibits connectivity in all the three directions).

In order to understand and characterize the effect of porosity on the overall response of (zero-dimensional (3-0), one-dimensional (3-1) and three-dimensional (3-3)) porous piezoelectric materials, several analytical [2-5], numerical [6-12] and experimental studies [13-17] have been conducted. For example, Dunn and Taya [2] developed analytical models to predict the electromechanical response of porous piezoelectric materials with zero-dimensional (3-0) and one-dimensional (3-1) connectivity. Banno [5] developed a theoretical model and derived expressions for the electromechanical properties of porous PZT ceramic with three-dimensional connectivity (3-3) as a function of porosity. Iyer and Venkatesh [7] developed a unit-cell based finite element models to study the effect of porosity shape on the

electromechanical response of 3-0 type porous piezoelectric materials. Kar-Gupta and Venkatesh [8] developed a unit-cell based finite element model to study 3-1 type porous piezoelectric materials and demonstrated that the pore shape and orientation can significantly influence the performance of 3-1 type porous piezoelectric materials. Challagulla and Venkatesh [11] studied the effect of volume fraction, interconnect geometry and architecture of the piezoelectric foam structures on the electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures. More recently, Bosse et al. [12] developed a unit-cell based finite element model to study the effect of foam shape and porosity aspect ratio on the electromechanical response of 3-3 piezoelectric foams. Bast and Wersing [13] synthesized porous piezoelectric materials with 3-1 type connectivity and demonstrated that the acoustic impedance decreases with increased porosity. Bowen et al. [16] studied the effect of pore size and demonstrated experimentally that porous piezoelectric materials exhibit high hydrostatic figures of merit. Boumchedda et al. [17] fabricated 3-3 type porous PZT ceramics and concluded that cellular ceramics with higher volume fraction of porosity exhibited better hydrostatic characteristics compared to porous ceramics with lower porosity volume fraction.

Overall, a comprehensive set of analytical and numerical models and experimental results demonstrate that 3-3 type porous piezoelectric materials exhibit a combination of properties that are desirable for practical applications such as hydrophones. However, the effect of porosity shape and porosity volume fraction on the overall electromechanical response of 3-3 porous piezoelectric foams has not yet been fully

ascertained. Hence, the objectives of the present study are:

- (i) to develop a unit-cell based finite element model to study the behavior of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams (Fig. 1);
- (ii) to systematically study the effects of porosity geometry and porosity volume fraction on the effective electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams;
- (iii) to quantify the effects of porosity geometry and porosity volume fraction on the effective figures of merit of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams.

In the present study, to identify the effects of porosity shape on the effective electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams, nine types of porosity shapes are examined (Fig. 2).

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. An overview of the constitutive relations that describe the coupled behaviour of piezoelectric materials is presented in Section 2. Selected figures of merit of porous piezoelectric materials that are relevant to device applications are identified in Section 3. Section 4 describes the finite element model developed to characterize the electromechanical response of piezoelectric foam structures. The trends observed are presented in Section 5 and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Constitutive Behavior of Piezoelectric Materials

The electromechanical response of piezoelectric materials in the linear elastic domain is captured by the coupled constitutive relationships represented by:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}^E \epsilon_{kl} - e_{ijk} E_k \\ D_i &= e_{ikl} \epsilon_{kl} + \kappa_{ij}^E E_j \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where σ and ϵ are second-order stress and strain tensors, respectively, C^E is fourth-order elasticity tensor with superscript "E" indicating elasticity tensor corresponding to measurement of C at constant/zero electric field, e is the third order coupling tensor, E is the electric field vector, D is electric displacement vector and κ^E is second-order

permittivity tensor measured at constant/zero strain. The subscripts i, j, k, l varies from 1 to 6. Eq. (1) can be represented by a matrix using the following mapping of adjacent indices: $11 \rightarrow 1, 22 \rightarrow 2,$

$33 \rightarrow 3, 23 \rightarrow 4, 13 \rightarrow 5, 12 \rightarrow 6,$ as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ D_1 \\ D_2 \\ D_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11}^E & C_{12}^E & C_{13}^E & C_{14}^E & C_{15}^E & C_{16}^E & -e_{11} & -e_{21} & -e_{31} \\ \cdot & C_{22}^E & C_{23}^E & C_{24}^E & C_{25}^E & C_{26}^E & -e_{12} & -e_{22} & -e_{32} \\ \cdot & \cdot & C_{33}^E & C_{34}^E & C_{35}^E & C_{36}^E & -e_{13} & -e_{23} & -e_{33} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & C_{44}^E & C_{45}^E & C_{46}^E & -e_{14} & -e_{24} & -e_{34} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & C_{55}^E & C_{56}^E & -e_{15} & -e_{25} & -e_{35} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & C_{66}^E & -e_{16} & -e_{26} & -e_{36} \\ e_{11} & e_{12} & e_{13} & e_{14} & e_{15} & e_{16} & \kappa_{11}^E & \kappa_{12}^E & \kappa_{13}^E \\ e_{21} & e_{22} & e_{23} & e_{24} & e_{25} & e_{26} & \cdot & \kappa_{22}^E & \kappa_{23}^E \\ e_{31} & e_{32} & e_{33} & e_{34} & e_{35} & e_{36} & \cdot & \cdot & \kappa_{33}^E \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ 2\epsilon_{23} \\ 2\epsilon_{13} \\ 2\epsilon_{12} \\ E_1 \\ E_2 \\ E_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) is the most general representation of the constitutive behavior of piezoelectric materials and has 21 elasticity, 18 piezoelectric and 6 permittivity constants that are independent material properties. Thus a complete characterization of piezoelectric foam in the linear elastic domain requires an identification of all 45 independent constants.

3. Figures of Merit

To assess the utility of piezoelectric foam structures for practical applications such as hydrophones, several combinations of figures of merit derived from the fundamental material constants are typically employed. The figures of merit that are of direct interest to piezoelectric foam structures and their potential applications (e.g., hydrophones) are (i) the piezoelectric coupling constant (k_p); (ii) the acoustic impedance (Z); (iii) the piezoelectric charge coefficient (d_h); (iv) and the hydrostatic figure of merit (d_{hg}), and are described in detail in [11].

4. Three-Dimensional Finite Element Model for Piezoelectric Foam Structures

A unit-cell based three-dimensional finite element model is developed to characterize complete electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures over a range of porosity shapes and porosity volume fractions using a commercially available software ABAQUS. Eight-node, linear piezoelectric brick elements (C3D8E) are utilized for the piezoelectric foam structures where each node is allowed four degrees of freedom (three

translational and one electric potential). It is assumed that the piezoelectric material is poled in 2-direction.

In general, the modeling approach for predicting the properties of piezoelectric foams involves the following five steps: (i) a unit cell that is appropriate for a foam structure with a specified volume fraction and porosity shape is identified (Fig. 1); (ii) the unit cell is subjected to controlled mechanical and electrical loading conditions under carefully designed boundary conditions (Fig. 3); (iii) the stress and electric displacements field developed in the unit cell as a result of applied strain and electric fields in the unit cell are measured; (iv) appropriate average procedures are invoked to capture the homogeneous coupled response of the unit cell; (v) using the matrix representation of the coupled response of piezoelectric materials, where the measured stress and electric displacements are related to the imposed strain and electric fields through the constitutive material property matrix, all the piezoelectric material constants are computed [8].

In the unit-cell based finite element model, to characterize electromechanical response of 3-3 piezoelectric foam structures it is important to ensure that the deformation characteristics of the microscopic unit cell are representative of the deformation of the macroscopic foam structures. Hence, to ensure that the deformation and electric potential across the boundaries of the representative unit cell is compatible with the deformation of the adjacent unit cells, the following constraint equations are identified (Fig. 3), where the nodes A (AA), B (BB), C (CC), D (DD) are designated as master nodes and u refers to all four degrees of freedom (i.e., $u = 1, 2, 3$ and 9):

(i) For periodicity in the 1-direction:

$$\begin{aligned} u^R - u^A &= u^S - u^B; u^{RR} - u^{AA} = u^{SS} - u^{BB}; \\ u^V - u^A &= u^W - u^B; u^{VV} - u^{DD} = u^{WW} - u^{CC} \\ &; u^{XM} - u^A = u^{XP} - u^B. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) For periodicity in the 2-direction:

$$\begin{aligned} u^U - u^A &= u^{UU} - u^{AA}; u^S - u^B = u^{SS} - u^{BB}; \\ u^{YM} - u^A &= u^{YP} - u^{AA}. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) For periodicity in the 3-direction:

$$\begin{aligned} u^T - u^D &= u^U - u^A; u^{TT} - u^{DD} = u^{UU} - u^{AA}; \\ u^W - u^B &= u^{WW} - u^C; u^{ZM} - u^B = u^{ZP} - u^C. \end{aligned}$$

5. Results and Discussions

Three-dimensional finite element model developed in Section 4 is implemented to study the effect of porosity shape and porosity volume fraction on the electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foam. PZT-7A is selected as a model material for the present study (Table 1). Figs 4 and 5 present the variation of fundamental elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric constants and figure of merit with increasing material volume fraction for 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures over a range of porosity shapes. The principal observations are summarized as follows:

- (i) The fundamental elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric constants, in general, increase nonlinearly with increase in material volume fraction (with the exception of κ_{11} and κ_{33} for foam structures with circular porosity).
- (ii) In general, the principal electromechanical properties in the longitudinal direction (i.e., along the poling direction) such as C_{22} , κ_{22} and e_{22} are higher for the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=4a$ and lower for the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=0.25a$.
- (iii) The principal electromechanical properties in the transverse direction (i.e., perpendicular to the poling direction) such as C_{11} and κ_{11} are higher for the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=0.25a$ and lower for the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=4a$.
- (iv) The principal electromechanical property, C_{33} (in the transverse direction) is higher for the piezoelectric foams with circular shaped porosity and lower for the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped

porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=0.25a$ and $b=4a$.

- (v) The shear elastic constants such as C_{12} , C_{13} , C_{23} are higher for the foam structures with circular shaped porosity.
- (vi) In general, the figures of merit (i.e. k_t , Z , d_{hp} and d_{hg_h}) for bulk PZT-7A can be enhanced significantly by increasing the porosity volume fraction.
- (vii) For higher material volume fraction (greater than 62%), the piezoelectric foams with rectangular and ellipsoidal shaped porosity with porosity aspect ratio of $b=4a$ exhibits higher piezoelectric coupling constant (k_t).
- (viii) Piezoelectric foams with square shaped porosity exhibits higher hydrostatic figure of merit (d_{hg_h}) at low material volume fractions.

6. Conclusions

Porous piezoelectric material, especially 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures demonstrate enhanced figures of merit such as the piezoelectric charge coefficient (d_h), hydrostatic voltage coefficient (g_h), and hydrostatic figure of merit (d_{hg_h}), and are desirable for certain practical applications such as hydrophones. However, the effect of porosity shape and porosity volume fraction on the overall electromechanical response of 3-3 porous piezoelectric foams has not yet been fully ascertained. Hence, the present study was focused on obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the role of porosity shape and porosity volume fraction on the effective properties of piezoelectric foams. In general, the effective electromechanical properties of the foam structures and their corresponding figures of merit were shown to be strongly dependent on the porosity shape and porosity volume fraction.

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Table 1. Fundamental elastic, piezoelectric, and dielectric properties of the model material PZT-7A chosen for the present study.

	PZT-7A ($\rho=7700 \text{ kg/m}^3$)
$C_{11}^E = C_{33}^E$ (GPa)	148
$C_{12}^E = C_{23}^E$ (GPa)	74.2
C_{13}^E (GPa)	76.2
C_{22}^E (GPa)	131
$C_{44}^E = C_{66}^E$ (GPa)	25.3
C_{55}^E (GPa)	35.9
$e_{21} = e_{23}$ (C/m ²)	-2.324
e_{22} (C/m ²)	10.9
$e_{34} = e_{16}$ (C/m ²)	9.31
$\kappa_{11}^e = \kappa_{33}^e$ (nC/Vm)	3.98
κ_{22}^e (nC/Vm)	2.081

Fig. 1. Schematic illustrating 3-3 type piezoelectric foam and corresponding unit-cell.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustrating 9 types of piezoelectric foams based on porosity shape (for 30% porosity volume fraction).

Fig. 3. Schematic representing various node sets indentified for the finite element modeling of the 3-3 type piezoelectric foams.

Fig. 4. Variation of fundamental elastic, dielectric, and piezoelectric properties of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams with material volume fraction.

Fig. 5. Variation of select figures of merit of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams with material volume fraction.